

Making the Connections: A Teacher Educator's Perspective on Compatibility of English Language Teaching Methods

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ABSTRACT

This article is based on my keynote presentation at the *16th University of Sydney TESOL Research Colloquium* in 2024. Teaching about the range of methods that characterise our field is standard in any Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL) education course. Common texts provide teacher educators with guidance on how to raise learners' awareness of the origins of methods, their similarities and differences, and the advantages and challenges of using these methods to teach English to linguistically diverse learners. However, while such texts and other resources help develop an understanding of various TESOL methods, I found that very few provide guidance on how to teach our learners about the compatibility of these methods with their own contexts. Just as there is no correlation between proficiency levels in English language macro skills, experience in teaching English as an additional or foreign language does not guarantee sufficient levels of proficiency in English language teaching methods. In this session, I will share with you my self-study story on ways I approach and develop the teaching of TESOL methods to a linguistically diverse cohort of postgraduate students. At the core of my approach is the adaptation of a critical

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reflection framework to inform course design, which enables students to make stronger connections between theory and practice. My journey as a teacher educator continues, and I will discuss the implications of this approach for helping our students make connections by exploring the compatibility of the content, making it both meaningful and transformational for their own teaching contexts.

Keywords: contextualisation, critical reflection, professional identity, reflective practice, teacher education, TESOL methods

INTRODUCTION

Teacher educators often inhabit liminal spaces, negotiating between research, practice, and teaching-intensive responsibilities. While much of the scholarship foregrounds the contributions of research-focused academics, there is value in considering how teaching-focused academics engage with, and make connections to, research in ways that shape student learning and professional growth. The aim of the keynote address I gave at the 2024 University of Sydney TESOL Research Colloquium was to share my own journey as a teacher and teacher educator, and to describe a reflective framework I use to help postgraduate TESOL students work out what will and will not fit their own teaching situations: acknowledging the things that inform our teaching practice and teacher identity. While it was a big honour to be invited to speak at the event, I felt intimidated; the impostor syndrome indicator was ticking up. However, putting those feelings aside, I reflected deeply on who I am now and what I have done to get to this point. I am one of those academics defined as teaching-intensive, meaning that around 80% of my academic work involves teaching. The requirement to undertake significant research is less for me than for many of my peers. Can you see why I sometimes feel like an impostor among researchers and budding researchers? As mentioned, interpretations of perspectives and our interactions with these interpretations are core to understanding our value and the value of our contributions to our social world.

Thus, it occurred to me that while we often hear from academics with well-established research identities, it is also important to hear from those whose job it is to make connections between the work of researchers and those who are impacted or those who will use the research to impact others—the teacher educator. As a teacher educator, I share my story of how I help my students make meaningful connections in my TESOL methods subjects and throughout my teaching. Core to my story are two main factors: the role the process of negotiating

our professional identities plays in teacher education, and the value of creating a reflective space to explore this process as we develop our knowledge and understanding of TESOL methods. My story does not rely heavily on a specific research methodology, but it is informed by research. You could say that it reflects the spirit of ethnography, the study of cultural patterns and behaviours to understand the complex social world in which I live. Thus, here is my story, comprised of 4 episodes.

EPISODE 1: THE TEACHER: YOU'RE DR WHO?

We all have a starting point in our teacher education journey. Here is mine. The starting point for my story is my broad research interest in exploring professional identity. It has come to underpin all that I do in my teaching. This was the research topic of my doctoral studies. The inclination to explore this area has always fascinated me, possibly because I am drawn to understanding what drives people's actions and what shapes them as individuals. Since deciding to follow a career in teaching, the number one participant in all my observations has been me. Thus, in the spirit of ethnography and following the theme of professional identity, let me bring you up to speed on who I am.

I had never considered teaching as a career, let alone one in academia. My path beyond high school was limited due to my failure in the Higher School Certificate (HSC), the final exams we take at the end of our high school days in NSW. English was my weakest subject. This result defined me and shaped my perception of my intelligence for many years. It seemed I was destined for something less than greatness, but I was lucky to have whatever came my way, so I stuck with it.

So, I spent 8 of my post-HSC years working for a bank, until my sister secretly sent off a university application on my behalf. Unknowingly, stars began to align. Three years later, I earned a business degree with a major in tourism. My dream was to travel the world for the rest of my life and what better way than to have a job in tourism. Moreover, when I graduated, I had a plum government job waiting for me with Tourism NSW, but a little advertisement caught my attention to teach English in Taiwan. What better way to improve my English than to teach it!

After a coin toss, and in the blink of an eye, I was on my way to Taiwan. Virtually untrained, definitely inexperienced, and still with the stigma of having failed English in my final year at school (though I did leave university with a distinction average), I was standing at the front of a classroom, filled with young learners and

their parents, ready to be taught English by this newly arrived native speaker teacher. My one semester of postgraduate study in TESOL, which I managed to fit in just before leaving Australia, did not cover this scenario! How could that Derewianka SFLish text and context class help with teaching present simple tense dialogue about things we eat for breakfast? I was not making any connections. Halfway through the first class, I politely excused myself and found the first cubicle in the men's toilet where I collapsed on the floor in absolute fear. What the hell had I got myself into? What is going to get me out of this one?

Let us stop here to make some connections.

I present the pieces to my identity puzzle: Me with my self-assigned label of school failure. Worked in a bank. Completed an undergraduate degree, beyond expectations. Added a postgraduate qualification in TESOL to my resume. Which of these had the most significant impact on me, do you think, while I was on the floor of the cubicle, reflecting on my identity as an English teacher in a Taiwanese conversation school for mostly unmotivated adolescents? Over the course of eight years, I worked in an environment where quality service was at the core of every activity we did. Checks and balances ensured that customers' needs were always met effectively, efficiently, and to a high standard. If this were absent in my DNA after my time in the bank, I would have been on the next plane out of Taiwan. Despite the academic success and the brief training, it was this experience that pulled me through. That and my dad's parting words, someone who, as a metal fabrication teacher with a healthy level of scepticism of universities, told me that to be a good teacher, "you gotta know what you are talking about".

So, I made the commitment to do my best, which meant learning how to teach English. In this context, English language teaching at a cram school in Taiwan was heavily influenced by the traditional approach, and many local Taiwanese teachers adhered closely to the teacher-centred approach, undertaking the bulk of the teaching work with a heavy reliance on Mandarin as the language of instruction. As a native English speaker, I was the novelty act, coming in and essentially being the clown who built on the work of the Taiwanese teacher. What made this school unique, too, was that parents could sit in the back and learn English alongside their children. Most of the time, the kids were asleep, their heads on their desks, while the parents diligently took their notes. It was a case of 2 for the price of 1 as the parents were more motivated than the students to learn English. Grammar structures were taught through choral drilling with accuracy one week, only to be forgotten the following week. It was a time of very steep learning on how to teach

English. I developed my own values regarding methods of teaching and learning English as a foreign language, tailored to this specific context, believing that students needed to have a choice. An understanding of the motivational factors that contribute to their learning needs to be identified and acknowledged. Furthermore, they needed to work at their own level. I began to reflect on the communicative approach to teaching language and a more autonomous approach to learning language. However, I still lacked the depth of knowledge about appropriate pedagogy at that stage. I had huge arguments with the local teachers who told me that the students should not be taught my way, that the Taiwanese knew the right way to teach. Maybe they were right. I was still green.

Let me fast-forward now, past the two years I spent working in an English-medium instruction kindergarten, still in Taiwan, where I oversaw 16 three-year-olds who spoke no English. And with no qualifications in early childhood education. Back in Australia, I pursued a Master of Education in TESOL, as I believed that to stick to this career path, I needed to gain more knowledge and qualifications. Let us skip over most of my eight years in Japan, where I worked at two universities, teaching English to mostly unmotivated students. Nevertheless, let us stop briefly towards the end of my time there. This is where I began my doctoral studies, marking the start of my journey to understand how our professional identities are shaped by a complex process of interpreting interactions within past, present, and future experiences. However, once again, my time in the bank informed the genesis of my doctoral studies. How can we provide learners with value for money? What makes a good teacher? Not just any teacher of English, but one who has committed to a career of teaching English in tertiary contexts, in my case, Japan. What informs the negotiation of professional identities of teachers of English in Japan?

Undertaking my doctorate at UOW, I was surrounded by significant theoretical forces, including Bakhtin, Bourdieu, Foucault, and ubiquitous sociocultural theory. All of which I struggled to grasp, though I did enjoy Foucault's writings on incarceration. Instead, I was drawn to symbolic interactionism. It is a theoretical framework informed by the work of Mead (1934), who was aligned with the University of Chicago. You will not find a great deal of his publications because he did not publish a great deal. Instead, he preferred to share his research through presentations and lectures. His theories fall within the field of social psychology, although there is little evidence that he defined himself as a social psychologist.

The central premise of symbolic interactionism is that social reality is constructed through the interactions and meanings that individuals assign to symbols,

language, and gestures in their everyday lives. It emphasises the importance of understanding how people interpret and give meaning to their experiences and how these interpretations shape social behaviour and relationships. Essentially, it suggests that human behaviour is influenced by the social context and the meanings individuals derive from their interactions with others. If you think you have heard something like this before, it is because a lot of what Mead shared was very similar to that of Vygotsky (Lantolf, 2000). There is no evidence that the two ever met, but comparing the principles of symbolic interactionism with those of sociocultural theory reveals a significant overlap. We could be mistaken in thinking that Mead and Vygotsky were playing a game of 'anything you can do, I can do better.' I will leave that argument for the theoretical purists on either side.

I was drawn to symbolic interactionism because it made sense to me and seemed appropriate for the world I wanted to explore. It seemed a nice fit for a sticky beak like me to explore the professional identities of teachers established in their careers of teaching English in Japan. Symbolic interactionism provided me with insight into how others perceive the teaching of English in specific contexts, specifically in the foreign language teaching context at a Japanese university. Through my research, I found that they drew on not only their own language learning experiences but also a complex matrix of other factors that informed their teaching practice. As part of this negotiating process, many were challenged by local customs and local approaches to teaching English and the education system. Context mattered. However, more than context, such as my own extensive banking experience, many non-educational factors also played a significant role in how they negotiated their identities as English teachers. From this, a spark was born.

Our professional identity influences the way we interpret our interactions with TESOL concepts as we grow and develop in our roles as English teachers. However, something was missing. How can we characterise this process of interpreting our interactions with the range of objects —social, physical, and abstract — that contribute to our growth? How were they making these meaningful connections?

EPISODE 2: THE CONTEXT: FINDING MY FOOTING

It is now time to put me into context. Let me set the scene. Allow me to transport you to the wonderful world of the University of Wollongong's TESOL postgraduate programme. Our student cohort is wide-ranging. Domestic and international. From the inexperienced to the very experienced. As is often the case in higher education, we move and teach between subjects within our TESOL program. One sunny day,

not too long ago, I was invited to take over the subject of Methods in Second Language Learning. Your standard methods subject is popular with many. A core component of several of our TESOL courses. A great opportunity, but one that I was apprehensive about accepting. We know that just because a language learner can speak well, their ability to write in the target language does not always correlate with their speaking ability. Similarly, just because I can teach English, and English is my first language, does not mean I know how to teach the methods that inform my teaching. Especially when it is not my area of research. I was filled again with doubt. We teachers often doubt our abilities, don't we? I was mentally dialling the identity crisis hotline. Not only about ways to teach a methods class in TESOL, but what did I know about TESOL methods that I could teach? More broadly, what was my area of expertise, what was my thing that I could bring to this subject? I work with colleagues who are experts in pronunciation, functional grammar, and neuroscience. What was my thing? I have a PhD in professional identity. Where is the value in that? It is not as sexy as, say, doing the dialogic approach the Wotring way (Wotring et al., 2024). Thus, when I was asked to teach methods, I had no idea what my area of expertise was at that stage that would inform my take on teaching methods and add value. The banking DNA was driving a need to maintain a sense of quality and service. Challenge accepted! I always take on tasks that are beyond my capabilities. That is how we grow, I suppose.

So, my first semester of teaching methods was literally by the book. The Jeremy Harmer textbook 'The Practice of English Language Teaching, 5th edition' (Harmer, 2015). Well known through its many iterations. As is the case when subjects are passed on, I inherited teaching materials from the previous coordinator.

For the first semester, I was essentially parroting what was given to me without truly connecting with much of the content. It began by defining and explaining popular TESOL methods, such as communicative language teaching (CLT), task-based language teaching (TBLT), and content language integrated learning (CLIL) (Harmer, 2015). I had been aware of these concepts, which I incorporated into my teaching at various points in my career, dating back to my time in Taiwan. However, I still thought the depth of my conceptual knowledge was questionable. The textbook and other sources provided sufficient information to begin building conceptual knowledge and introducing students to the topics, but something was still missing – something was not just connecting. As teachers, we need to bring that content to life, help our students make connections, and, more importantly, ensure it is relevant to their contexts. I needed to examine the connections more closely to make them meaningful.

I attempted to create interactive lessons, informed by the methods we discussed, to demonstrate and evaluate, but something was still missing. What did they need to trigger that meaningful process? What a goofball! I thought. I was so focused on conveying the content that I overlooked the simple fact that I was teaching teachers, or people who aspired to be teachers. So stupid me, of course. TESOL teacher education courses like ours are great, focusing on what and how to teach English, but perhaps they are a bit light on the 'who'. Found my thing! Engaging their professional identity involves negotiating the objects that shape their self-perception as English teachers, how others perceive them, and how these interactions inform their teaching practices. Thus, that was the trigger that I needed. To then find that connection that brings about this process, and of course, I had it right in front of me: Critical reflection.

EPISODE 3: CAN I HAVE THE ROOM? MAKING THE CONNECTIONS IN THE REFLECTIVE SPACE

It was an area of research that I started as a casual academic to keep me from going balmy, taking on marking jobs for other academics. Fresh from submitting my thesis, I naively volunteered to mark essays in one of our preservice teacher education courses in our first-year subjects. Core to all the essay tasks was the requirement to reflect on various teaching concepts critically. After marking nearly 1000 essays over the course of one semester, I realised that the students could not write critical reflections. They wrote reflections, but they did not write critical reflections. Why couldn't they write a critical reflection? More puzzling, why not simply Google 'how to write a critical reflection'? This sparked my interest in examining critical reflection as a concept and exploring how learned knowledge can be demonstrated through a critical reflection lens, primarily through writing. They needed a useful tool or resource. Reflection was an assumed concept, something that everybody knew how to do. Reflection was a common element throughout many teacher education subjects, including TESOL. Despite this shared understanding and commonly used concept, there was very little guidance on teaching how to write a critical reflection or assess critical reflection writing. For UOW students, I needed to come up with something that I could teach them about both the concept and as a genre of writing. However, offer something that would not be clunky, that would not be a colour-by-numbers type of approach to writing. Something that would provide them with the factors to consider for inclusion, while also giving them the freedom to be creative. So, how do I differentiate between reflection and critical reflection? I am glad you asked.

Reflection is a complex process that involves interpreting events and experiences of the past in the context of the present, informing future action and behaviour (Blumer, 1986). According to Brookfield (2017), however, reflection is not, by definition, critical. Critical reflection, as a concept, is situated further along the continuum of reflection, with a greater emphasis on encouraging movement beyond recollections and observations towards analysis, action, and change. Described as a complex, rigorous, intellectual, and emotional enterprise (Rodgers, 2002, p. 844), it provides space to explore 'both personal and professional belief systems' (Larrivee, 2008, p. 343). While critical reflection's value and role in teacher education have been well documented (e.g., Körkkö et al., 2016; Liu, 2015; Ramlal & Augustin, 2020), less clear is how students can effectively demonstrate their ability to reflect critically on experiential learning in their writing.

The works of Brookfield (2017), Dewey (Dewey, 1910), and Schön (Schön, 2017) informed my understanding of critical reflection as a concept, in addition to the work of Ryan and Ryan (2014) and Bain et al. (2002) to help develop learning resources focused on critical reflection writing. While my conceptual understanding remains aligned with these reference points, I found that during this self-exploration, a fundamental tension emerged between my conceptual knowledge and its application in teaching and assessing critical reflection writing at the graduate level. Ryan's (2011) critical reflection writing framework, for example, draws on a systemic functional linguistic (SFL) perspective, comprised of four text types: recount, description, explanation, and discussion (Ryan, 2011, p. 104). Each text type has particular language features.

Teacher education programmes often lack a sufficient structure or framework to develop critical reflection that effectively contributes to transformative learning. Schön's (2017) popular concepts of reflection in action and reflection on action have been used widely in teacher education to raise awareness about the value of the relationship between critical reflection and teaching practice. Although the literature on critical reflection and suggested frameworks for developing reflective practices are growing, few provide clear guiding frameworks for developing writing practices that demonstrate critical reflection.

Viola! I came up with something very simple. Perhaps too simple, but this critical reflection framework (Fraser et al., 2024) enables me to clarify what I mean by critical reflection and what is expected when students write a critical reflection. It has three points, as all triangles do. Furthermore, each point represents key elements of a critical reflection. The process begins with an experience or episode,

something personal to them, relatable, and about which they have extensive knowledge. They are then asked to describe and explore that experience through the lens of theoretical concepts that relate to it. This provides greater depth to their experience, enabling them to gain a more nuanced understanding of that experience that aligns with the broader research literature. And then? Through that process of meaning-making, one starts to look to the future. How does this meaning-making contribute to the negotiation process of developing their professional identities? To develop their teaching practices that meet the expectations of others in their target teaching contexts? The critical reflection aims to prompt them to explore who they are in the present, drawing on something from the past, but to bring about a transformation that will propel them further into the future in a more developed way. Thus, that is my critical reflection.

That was the easy bit. The challenge has been to find common ground where we can share understanding and engage in conceptual discussions. It is taking me some time to find that ground, to build that ground – let me keep the metaphor going – to fertilise and nurture that ground. I am still getting there, but the tools, compost, and fertiliser that I have been using to work this ground consist of developing students' abilities to look for compatibility in what we are discussing. It has been a common remark that students who pass through our program, particularly the international students, enjoy learning and engaging with the new perspectives, and, only to return to their home contexts, feel they have little opportunity to implement this new learning (Pham & Saito, 2019). This issue is one that I have been trying to address in all my TESOL teaching. How to make what they do and learn here have meaning back there? How to make it compatible? A critical reflection thread throughout my subject design creates a productive reflective space that facilitates discussions that explore this issue.

Setting off down a rabbit hole, where I think I am still traversing, I explored that process, starting with a self-study of the critical reflection concept (Fraser, 2021). If I wanted my students to frame their discourse through critical reflection, I needed to gain a deeper insight into the concept that would inform my teaching methods. More importantly, the goal is for students to find value in the concept for their own personal growth and development.

Our interactions with the past help us to interpret the present, which, in turn, informs our future behaviour as teachers. My self-study provided a small but meaningful piece to my complex identity as a teacher educator by allowing me to pay closer attention to my teaching practices. Self-study in teacher education

practices (S-STEP) aims to explore and expand the knowledge base of teacher educators (LaBoskey, 2004). LaBoskey (2004, p. 839) argues that as educators of teachers, “we have a pedagogical responsibility to monitor our progress continuously; to check for discrepancies between our ideals and our practice [in ways that] ... result in, or not, the reframed thinking and practice of our students and ourselves”. While self-study is an established methodology for practitioner inquiry within language education scholarship, with the dual purpose of optimising practice and contributing to a grounded and public knowledge base of language teacher education, its presence at the graduate level is underdeveloped.

Now, you are probably wondering about the trustworthiness of such a study. Well, I am glad you asked. Being a self-study, I was uniquely placed as both participant and researcher, which some may say challenges current notions of trustworthiness. However, having my back, Hamilton et al. (2020, p. 309) suggest that rather than focusing on the primary research relationship between the researcher and the academy, the focus should be on the relationship between the researcher’s world in which they live and practice. I constantly triangulated my journal data and margin notes with the research findings, the analysis of reflective posts made by my students in a blog and in their assessment tasks, and the research literature around critical reflection writing. Further triangulation, common to S-STEP, such as working with a critical friend, would have been beneficial in strengthening the trustworthiness of my data interpretation and providing suitable models for collaborative self-study work. Yet, I am to have that conversation with my critical friend, so my work is still in progress.

From my dalliance with critical reflection as a concept, I found that conceptual knowledge requires significantly more time than a semester, which we already know. However, creating reflective space can lay some important foundations upon which knowledge can grow beyond the subject. This is something that is rarely covered in any textbook that informs teaching TESOL methods. The development of conceptual knowledge is a process that needs time. The contributing factors that determine the length of time are our abilities to make things compatible through contextualisation, developed through engaging in critical reflection.

Reflective space is core to fostering effective growth and meaningful transformation of a teacher’s professional identity and teaching practice. The reflective space I identified in my subject design is characterised by the students’

abilities to interact with their interpretations of a range of social objects that would otherwise be constrained if they attempted to seek reflective practice during their regular teaching routines and environments. Removal from their typical contexts placed them in a kind of “zero room” environment, free from the weighty demands of teaching and administrative responsibilities usually constraining any form of deep, critical reflection on their teaching practices and who they are as teachers. Time constraints and pressures from work commitments limit a teacher’s ability to reflect meaningfully in a way that contributes to change. Within this reflective space, students can explore choices based on theoretical concepts relevant to their own teaching environments. However, this space is not constraint- or pressure-free. Students often begin their learning experiences with some level of anxiety due mainly to doubts about their abilities to undertake work at a postgraduate level and about their language abilities to write to the same level of expectations. However, our students are also highly supported within this space to address these limitations. An important factor in my subject is the use of scaffolding to minimise the impact of these doubts and maximise the opportunity for participants to develop confidence as they engage with the theoretical concepts.

More significantly, this opportunity allows my students to integrate their new ideas and teaching practices, applying the newly discovered theoretical principles within their respective teaching environments. The Methods subject, with critical reflection at its core, allows students to explore opportunities to meaningfully and sustainably integrate their knowledge into their teaching practices. The aim is not to revolutionise the entire education system, but rather to find a small yet suitably compatible way to enhance their teaching practices, to provide more effective learning experiences for their students.

The design of my methods class provides a reflective space for students to explore concepts and theories relevant to their own teaching environments, without the constraints common to their teaching contexts. Instead of transition, the process of critical reflection aims to bring about regeneration in both professional identity and teaching practice. Reflective space draws together threads of their past to be used in negotiations in the present, shaping future behaviour and practices that meet the expectations of becoming an English teacher in their respective educational contexts.

EPISODE 4: AND SO: CHALLENGES, CONSIDERATIONS, AND CONNECTIONS, OH MY!

Thus, my story comes to a close. A story about how I try to awaken my students to looking more closely at how their stories are evolving, making connections to understanding in greater depth their own professional identities as teachers of English. It is one that I am sure is familiar to many. The story of a teacher becoming: the doubts, the challenges, the growth, the success, the discoveries (often serendipitously). For me, it was through reflection that I have gained both a deeper understanding and greater appreciation of who I am becoming as a teacher. The way in which my professional identity informs my practice helps my students make their own connections. Of course, we personalise our teaching, informed by the infinite process of negotiating our professional identities, the complex matrix where experiences, knowledge, and perceptions of past, present and future interact.

Teaching methods are more than amplifying the pages of a textbook. It requires exploration of compatibility to make meaningful connections with conceptual knowledge and the complexity of real-world classrooms. There are challenges ahead in teaching English that will impact TESOL methods in teacher education. The affordances and challenges of using AI as a helpful tool in the language classroom are readily apparent. Learning English with the temptation of these emerging and impactful tools helps make connections beyond the local context and community, which is a significant factor in our teaching identity. It also has the potential to change the character of our community. For the better? Who is to know? As I teach the universal aspects of methods, I remind my students also to consider the impact. Reflect on the connections that will be made as a result of their teaching.

CONCLUSION

The three fundamental principles that inform my TESOL methods subject design (and the design of all of my teacher education subjects) are as follows. First, contextualisation is important. It is not just to help explain the methods. Getting students to draw on their respective contexts to explore more deeply the affordances and challenges. This process of interpretation provides the meaning with which we engage with the world. Second, it makes the job of finding compatibility a little less challenging. The realisation is that it is not about changing the system and turning it upside down. It is about finding inroads. It is about

finding opportunities to make the smallest transformation or have the smallest impact, yet achieve a meaningful impact in whichever teaching and learning environment we are practising. Third, the space in which all this happens, the realisation of context and the identification of opportunities for compatibility, takes place in a reflective space. At the core of making all this connected is the process of critical reflection. A magical thinking tool of infinite potential. I have found that it helps my students make those connections more meaningful. The feedback I receive from students indicates that, from their perspective, it makes their learning experiences more meaningful. However, more importantly, they can then take with them the knowledge they gain here and apply it in a meaningful way in their own context. I think that is how I perceive my role as a teacher educator, as a teaching-intensive academic. To provide those connections between the theory and practice, connections characterised by compatibility, contextualisation, and reflective space. It must be meaningful for me first before I can make it meaningful for others.

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